

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АНТИОКСИДТЕЛЬНЫХ СВОЙСТВ НЕКОТОРЫХ N-АЛКИЛАМИНОЗАМЕЩЕННЫХ ЭПИТИОСОЕДИНЕНИЙ

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STUDY OF THE ANTIOXIDATIVE PROPERTIES OF SOME N-ALKYLAMINE SUBSTITUTE EPITIO COMPOUNDS

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Аннотация

Продолжая исследования для соискания более эффективных многофункциональных присадок к нефтепродуктам и для того, чтобы определить взаимосвязь между строением синтезированных соединений и их антиокислительной активностью в качестве присадок к смазочным маслам, в данной статье мы попытались изучить антиокислительные свойства некоторых N-алкиламинозамещенных эпителиосоединений - 1,2-эпителио-3-N-алкиламинопропанов (алкиламинозамещенных тиранов) в модельных реакциях с кумилпероксидными радикалами и гидропероксидом кумола (ГПК). Научная новизна данной работы заключается в том, что впервые, нами были исследованы антиокислительные свойства N-алкиламинозамещенных тиранов в модельных реакциях ингибирования - в реакциях с кумилпероксидными радикалами и гидропероксидом кумола.

Abstract

Continuing research for more effective multifunctional additives to petroleum products and in order to determine the relationship between the structure of synthesized compounds and their antioxidant activity as additives to lubricating oils, in this article we tried to study the antioxidant properties of some N-alkylamino-substituted epithio compounds - 1,2-epithio-3-N-alkylaminopropanes (alkylamino-substituted thierans) in model reactions with cumyl peroxide radicals and cumene hydroperoxide (CHP). The analysis of the conducted studies makes it possible to predict that the alkylamino-substituted thirane synthesized by us, reacting with peroxide radicals, terminate the oxidation chains and catalytically destroy cumene hydroperoxide to molecular products. Therefore, alkylamino substituted thiranes can be used as antioxidant additives to petroleum products.

Ключевые слова: Алкиламины, тираны, антиокислительные присадки, алкиламинзамещенные тираны, тиозпихлоргидрин, тиозпоксидирование, кумилпероксид, гидропероксид кумола.

Keywords: Alkylamine, thiran, antioxidant additives, alkylamine substituted thierans, thioepichlorohydrin, thioepoxidation, cumyl peroxide, cumene hydroperoxide.

Introduction

To find new effective additives for lubricating oils, we have previously synthesized and studied a number of three+- and four-membered sulfur-containing heterocyclic compounds, thirans and thietanes, respectively [1–9].

However, N-substituted sulfur-containing small heterocycles - alkylamine-substituted thiranes are hardly studied for this purpose. However, N-substituted

sulfur-containing small heterocycles - alkylamine-substituted thiranes are hardly studied for this purpose. What is connected with a high probability of their impractical synthesis, which in most cases is accompanied with the polymerization of the target products. Since we have recently managed to synthesize some representatives of N-alkylamino-substituted thierans [10], it would be interesting to investigate their antioxidant properties in model reactions of inhibition of β -oxidation of hydrocarbons in reactions with cumyl peroxide

radicals and cumyl hydroperoxide (CHP). Because these compounds contain both alkyl radicals, a nitrogen atom, and a sulfur atom in the heterocycle, which contribute to their use as antioxidant additives, as is known from the literature [5-7].

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The scientific novelty of this work lies in the fact that for the first time, we studied the antioxidant properties of N-alkylamino-substituted thierans in model reactions of inhibition-oxidation of hydrocarbons in reactions with cumyl peroxide radicals and cumyl hydroperoxide.

We remind that the production of N-alkylamine-substituted thiranes by direct, single-stage synthesis -

Then, by reacting the obtained N-alkylamine substituted α -chlorohydrins with a suspension of sodium hydroxide in diethyl ether, the corresponding oxiranes, 1,2-epoxy-3-N-alkylamine propanes (1,2-epoxypropylalkylamines - I6-VIII 6) are formed:

Finally, thioepoxidation of the obtained oxiranes under the action of thiourea synthesizes the corresponding thiranes -1,2-epitio-3-N-alkylamine propanes (1,2-epithiopropylalkylamines - Ib - VIIIb):

The composition and properties of all synthesized compounds were proved by elemental analysis, purity by thin layer and gas-liquid chromatography, and structures by IR- and PMR-spectroscopic methods. The physicochemical properties of the synthesized thirans, as well as their lubricating properties as antiwear and extreme pressure additives, have been studied by us before (these data were also sent to the editorial office of Petrochemistry magazine in Moscow, but not yet published).

Continuing further research for more effective multifunctional additives to petroleum products, and in order to determine the relationship between the structure of synthesized compounds and their antioxidant activity as additives to lubricating oils, in this article we attempted to investigate the antioxidant properties of alkylamine-substituted thiranes in model reactions with cumyl-peroxide radicals and hydroperoxide cumene (HPC). It should be noted that to study the antioxidant properties of additives added to lubricating oils and fuels in real conditions is very difficult. Therefore, we investigated the antioxidant properties of the synthesized compounds in the known model reactions, as noted above.

As a model reaction, an oxidative reaction proceeded is used, the initiator α , α' -azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) in a solution of chlorobenzene at a temperature

the reaction of 1,2-epitio-3-chloropropane with aliphatic amines was not possible (the reaction is accompanied by polymerization), despite the fact that most O- and S-substituted thirans were synthesized in the same way [11]. Therefore, we are forced to synthesize N-alkylamino-substituted thierans stepwise - one of the classical methods for the synthesis of thierans [11]:

The synthesis was carried out on the basis of very affordable industrial products (1,2-epoxy-3-chloropropane-epichlorohydrin and primary aliphatic amines. First, the reaction of certain primary aliphatic amines with 1,2-epoxy-3-chloropropane, proceeding according to the rules of Kratzwski, produces the corresponding chlorhydrins are obtained (Ia - VIIIa):

of 60 °C. The oxidative reaction was studied in a monometric instrument, which compensated for the oxygen pressure by oxygen absorption [13, 14]. In all tests, the concentration of AIBN is stable and is 2.10⁻² mol / l. In order to evaluate the antioxidant activity of the synthesized compounds (Ib - VIIIb), their reactions with cumylperoxide radicals and cumene hydroperoxide were investigated.

The concentration of the studied compounds varies in the range of 0.5-1.0.10⁻⁴ mol / l. Based on the studies, it was found that the alkylamino-substituted thiranes synthesized by us slow down the initiation of cumene oxidation. Calculates the stoichiometric coefficient (f), based on the value of the induction period (τ):

$$f = \frac{\tau \cdot W_i}{[InH]_0}$$

The stoichiometric coefficient (f) is equal to the number of oxidation chains terminated by one inhibitor molecule or its conversion product.

W_i - is the rate of initiation and has a value of 2.10⁻⁷ mol / ls.

$[InH]_0$ - is the initial concentration of the inhibitor and has the expression mole / l.

k_7 - is the constant rate of reactions of the inhibitor with peroxide radicals and is calculated by the following formula (B) [14]:

$$\text{tg} \alpha = \frac{f \cdot k_7 \cdot [\text{InH}]_0}{k_2 \cdot [\text{RH}] \cdot W_\ell} \quad (\text{B})$$

$$k_7 = \frac{\text{tg} \alpha \cdot k_2 \cdot [\text{RH}] \cdot W_\ell}{f \cdot [\text{InH}]_0} \quad (\text{C})$$

$k_2=1,51 \text{ l/mol}\cdot\text{s}$ [14]; $[\text{RH}]=6,9 \text{ mol/l}$

The reactions of the synthesized alkylamino-substituted thiranes with cumene hydroperoxide were carried out in chlorobenzene solution and in nitrogen atmosphere at 110°C in various concentrations.

In fig. 1 shows the kinetic curves initiated by the oxidation of cumene.

Fig.1. Kinetic curves of cumene oxidation initiated by alkylamino-substituted thiranes (60°C ; $[\text{AIBN}] = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; $[\text{InH}] = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol/l}$; $I_a - [\text{InH}] = 0$)

Figure 2 shows the kinetic curves for the decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of alkylamino-substituted thierans.

Fig.2. Kinetic curves for the decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of alkylamino-substituted thierans (110°C ; $[\text{ROOH}] = 0,21 \text{ mol/l}$; $W_0 = 4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol/l}\cdot\text{s}$; $k = 0,25$)

Table gives the parameter values characterizing the antioxidant properties of the synthesized compounds.

Table

The value of the kinetic parameters of the reactions of alkylamino-substituted thierans with the general formula: $\text{Alk-NH-CH}_2\text{-CH-CH}_2$ (with cumene hydroperoxide (110°C) and peroxide radicals (60°C) $[\text{AIBN}] = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/l; $W_1 = 2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mol/l · s

№ compounds	Alk-	k , mol/l · s	ν	K_7 mol/l · s	f
IВ	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-}$	0,23	4500	1,52	1,47
IIВ	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH-}$	0,21	3200	2,82	1,32
IIIВ	First- $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{-}$	0,25	3500	2,59	1,41
IVВ	Sec- $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{-}$	0,24	3800	2,91	1,69
VВ	izo- $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{-}$	1,34	6920	4,76	2,21
VIВ	$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C-}$	1,88	9000	3,77	1,25

The dependence of the initial rate of consumption of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of 1,2-epitio-3-N- (tert-butylamine) propane (VIb) on its concentration is shown in Fig.3:

Fig.3. The dependence of the initial rate of consumption of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of 1,2-epitio-3-N- (tert-butylamine) propane (VIb) on its concentration (110°C ; $[\text{InH}] = \text{const}$)

RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

An analysis of the experiments and the studies performed makes it possible to predict that the alkylamino-substituted thiranes synthesized by us, reacting with peroxide radicals, terminate the oxidation chains and catalytically destroy cumene hydroperoxide to molecular products. Therefore, alkylamino substituted thiranes can be used as antioxidant additives to petroleum products. Because:

1. As can be seen from fig. 1, the alkylamino substituted thiranes (Ib – VIIIb) studied by us, reacting with cumene peroxide, slow down the oxidation process. In the absence of alkylamino-substituted thierans, cumene oxidation proceeds at a constant rate and there is no induction period. And with the addition of alkylamino-substituted thierans to the lubricating oil at a concentration of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol / l, the rate of oxygen absorption decreases.

From fig. 1, it can be seen that compound VIb has the largest induction period ($\tau = 265$ min) among the compounds studied. This is most likely due to the stability of the tert-butyl radical in comparison with other alkyl radicals. Similar phenomena are observed for other alkylamino-substituted thierans.

2. From the foregoing (Table 1) it turns out that not only alkylamino-substituted thiranes, but also their interaction products with cumyl peroxide radicals, have an inhibited effect and slow down the oxidation of cumene.

3. As a result of the research, it turned out that all the alkylamino-substituted thiranes synthesized by us decompose cumene hydroperoxide. The kinetic curves of the decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of the studied thierans have an S-shape characteristic of autocatalytic processes. It should be noted

that the kinetic curves for the decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide by aminothiols and phenol sulfides are also S-shaped [12].

4. As can be seen from Fig. 2, at first, in a certain period (10 min), although cumene hydroperoxide is consumed in a small amount and an induction period is obtained. And then the decomposition rate begins to decrease in accordance with the decrease in concentration. This phenomenon proves once again that the decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide in the presence of alkylamino-substituted thierans occurs due to decomposition products, which are formed in a certain induction period.

5. On the other hand (Fig. 3), it was found that the initial reaction rate of the catalytic decomposition of alkylamino-substituted thierans is the first order of the ratio of cumene hydroperoxide.

The value of the kinetic parameters of the reactions of the catalytic decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of alkylamino-substituted thierans is given in Table 1. An analysis of the data in this table confirms that all the alkylamino-substituted thiranes synthesized by us decompose cumene hydroperoxide molecules. Among the alkylamino-substituted thiranes, 1,2-epithio-3-N- (tert-butylamine) propane (VIv) - ($v = 9000$) shows the highest activity

The value indicates that one molecule of the product of the transformation of the investigated compound decomposes 3000-9000 molecules of cumene hydroperoxide.

The rate constants of the catalytic decomposition of cumene hydroperoxide under the action of the substance VI v (k) reach their maximum value: $k = 1.88$ l / mol s.

Analysis tab. 1, as well as the drawings, makes it possible to predict that the alkylamino-substituted thirans synthesized by us (Iv – VIIIv), reacting with peroxide radicals, terminate the oxidation chains and catalytically destroy cumene hydroperoxide to molecular products. Therefore, the alkylamino-substituted thiranes synthesized by us (Iv – VIIIv) can be used as antioxidant additives to petroleum products.

Thus, a comparison of the kinetic parameters of the reactions of alkylamino-substituted thiranes with cumene hydroperoxide and peroxide radicals shows that changing the position of the structure of the alkyl group does not have a significant effect on their antioxidant properties (compounds with alkyl radicals of a branched structure slightly superior to those with unbranched radicals). Since all synthesized alkylamino-substituted thiranes possess sufficiently good antioxidant properties, it can be assumed that the main carrier

of the antioxidant properties of these epithio compounds is the three-membered thirane cycle, more precisely, the reaction of the thirane cycle with cumene hydroperoxide and peroxide radicals.

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